

From the Sideline to the Spotlight: Black Coaches' Struggles for Leadership in NCAA Division I

Author: Charles J. Allen III

Affiliation: National University

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Abstract

This article presents a qualitative phenomenological study investigating the lived experiences of Black assistant coaches in NCAA Division I football programs, with a focus on the Southeastern United States. Despite the growing presence of African American athletes in college football, the head coaching ranks remain overwhelmingly White, reflecting persistent racial disparities in leadership opportunities. Guided by Institutional Theory and the concept of racial tasking, this study explores how Black coaches perceive and navigate systemic barriers to career advancement. Ten African American assistant coaches participated in semi-structured interviews and completed open-ended questionnaires. Data were analyzed using NVivo software and thematically coded to reveal key patterns. Findings highlight structural exclusion, inequitable role assignments, limited access to social capital, and enduring racial stereotypes that hinder upward mobility. Participants described a climate of discouragement and frustration, where opportunities to advance were obstructed not by merit but by ingrained institutional norms. This study contributes to the broader understanding of racial inequity in college athletics and offers implications for policy reform and diversity hiring practices. Recommendations include revisiting hiring committee composition, implementing accountability measures, and creating formal mentorship pipelines for minority coaches.

Keywords: College Football Coaching, Institutional Racism, Racial Tasking, Sport Leadership

In the landscape of NCAA Division I football, a stark contrast persists between the racial makeup of players and the racial composition of those in leadership positions. While African American athletes represent the majority of players on the field, White men overwhelmingly occupy head coaching and administrative roles. This disparity has raised serious questions about access, equity, and systemic bias within collegiate athletics. Although numerous diversity initiatives have emerged, including adaptations of the NFL's Rooney Rule and the NCAA's Office of Inclusion, progress remains slow and uneven. For many Black assistant coaches—particularly those serving as position coaches or coordinators—the path to head coaching roles is often marked by invisible barriers rooted in institutional norms and racialized expectations.

This study seeks to explore the lived experiences of African American assistant coaches in NCAA Division I football, focusing on how they perceive and navigate the systemic challenges that hinder their advancement to head coaching roles. Specifically, this research centers on assistant coaches in the Southeastern United States—home to some of the most competitive and tradition-bound football programs in the country. Through a qualitative phenomenological approach, this study captures the voices and stories of coaches who have long aspired to lead but remain on the margins of decision-making power.

Institutional theory provides a guiding framework for understanding how entrenched cultural norms and organizational structures contribute to these inequities. This framework suggests that hiring and promotion decisions are often shaped by institutionalized practices that privilege the status quo—namely, Whiteness and familiarity—over diversity and merit. Alongside institutional theory, the concept of racial tasking further illuminates how Black coaches are often funneled into roles that reinforce stereotypes, such as

disciplinarians or recruiters for Black athletes, rather than strategic decision-makers like offensive or defensive coordinators. These assignments can severely limit professional development opportunities and visibility—key prerequisites for head coaching consideration.

Despite their qualifications and desire to lead, Black assistant coaches face a cycle of underrepresentation, invisibility, and stagnation. This cycle not only impacts individual careers but also perpetuates a broader culture of exclusion in collegiate sports. As previous research has noted, the “Old Boys’ Club” dynamic within athletic departments and hiring committees often results in selections based on personal networks and perceived fit—criteria that subtly yet powerfully disadvantage minority candidates.

This study aims to fill a gap in the existing literature by focusing not just on statistical disparities but on the personal narratives of Black coaches themselves. By centering their voices, this research offers insights into the emotional toll, professional barriers, and coping strategies associated with pursuing leadership roles in an environment where advancement is often obstructed by implicit and explicit biases. Ultimately, the findings underscore the need for structural change in NCAA hiring practices and a renewed commitment to fostering equitable leadership pathways in college athletics.

Literature Review

Despite the high number of African American athletes participating in NCAA Division I football, African Americans remain grossly underrepresented in leadership roles such as head coaches and athletic directors. This discrepancy has prompted increasing scrutiny from scholars, media, and diversity advocates (Lapchick, 2023). The NCAA has instituted diversity initiatives, including the NCAA Presidential Pledge and related hiring reports, yet the leadership gap remains

largely unchanged. As of recent counts, fewer than 10% of NCAA Division I head football coaches are Black, despite Black athletes comprising over 50% of all football players at that level (Singer, 2005; Lapchick, 2023).

This underrepresentation is not merely statistical—it reflects embedded power structures and hiring practices that favor White candidates. Scholars argue that this disparity is perpetuated by longstanding institutional and cultural norms within collegiate athletics (Cunningham, 2010). This literature review synthesizes key findings across four themes: institutional theory and hiring practices, racial tasking and stereotypical role placement, the influence of social capital, and the psychological toll of leadership exclusion.

Institutional Theory and Hiring Practices

Institutional theory helps explain how systemic structures within NCAA athletics reproduce racial inequities in leadership. Institutions often prioritize candidates who “fit” established organizational norms, which in predominantly White athletic departments means favoring White male leadership candidates (Cunningham, 2012). Hiring decisions are thus guided by a logic of appropriateness—those who resemble existing leaders are seen as more trustworthy or capable, regardless of merit (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). As a result, African American coaches are frequently overlooked due to implicit biases about competence, demeanor, or leadership style (Singer & Cunningham, 2012).

Many hiring committees consist of former coaches, boosters, or administrators who recycle White-dominant professional networks and replicate familiar leadership profiles. Thus, the opportunity for meaningful diversity in head coaching roles becomes limited not by a lack of qualified Black candidates but by the persistence of racially coded hiring norms (Agyemang

& DeLorme, 2010). Even when NCAA institutions express a desire to diversify, structural inertia and unspoken expectations about leadership inhibit transformative change.

Beyond hiring, many African American coaches experience “racial tasking,” a phenomenon in which they are assigned roles that align with racial stereotypes. Specifically, Black assistant coaches are often designated as “recruiters” of Black athletes or as “disciplinarians,” positions that are perceived to reflect their supposed natural rapport with Black players (Belch, 2004). These roles, while critical, do not often lead to head coaching opportunities, which typically require experience as a coordinator or play-caller—roles that are disproportionately granted to White assistants (Cooper, 2012).

Racial tasking constrains professional development, limiting Black coaches’ access to the types of responsibilities that make candidates viable for head coaching roles. These patterns are reinforced by a cultural narrative that portrays White coaches as cerebral strategists and Black coaches as emotional motivators, creating a racialized division of labor on coaching staffs (Singer, 2005; Borland & Bruening, 2010).

Social Capital and Informal Networks

Social capital—the networks and relationships that facilitate professional mobility—is also a critical barrier for Black coaches. Many hiring decisions in NCAA football are based on “who you know,” and Black coaches are often excluded from the social circles of decision-makers (Day, 2022). This exclusion is not always deliberate, but the informal nature of hiring decisions privileges candidates with longstanding ties to athletic directors, boosters, or influential coaches—relationships that are often inaccessible to Black assistants due to decades of segregation in the coaching pipeline (Cunningham, 2012).

Networking events, mentorship programs, and coaching trees frequently reproduce existing power dynamics. For instance, when prominent White head coaches promote assistants into coordinator roles, those assistants are more likely to be White—resulting in a cycle where Black coaches remain trapped in lateral roles (Smith, 2007). The concept of the “Old Boys’ Club” is thus not a metaphor but a functional reality in NCAA football hiring.

Numerous studies have identified the emotional toll of persistent underrepresentation and racialized role expectations. Black assistant coaches report feelings of frustration, burnout, and professional stagnation when repeatedly passed over for promotions despite comparable or superior qualifications (Beamon & Bell, 2002). Many internalize the belief that they must be “twice as good” to receive half the opportunity, an exhausting psychological burden that compounds over time (Singer, 2005).

This pressure can lead to disillusionment or resignation from the profession altogether, contributing to the “leaky pipeline” that reduces the pool of eligible Black head coaching candidates (Borland & Bruening, 2010). Moreover, tokenism—being the only Black coach on a staff or in a department—further isolates individuals and hinders opportunities for authentic professional growth.

Existing Interventions and Limitations

The NCAA has implemented initiatives such as the Presidential Pledge and TIDES (The Institute for Diversity and Ethics in Sport) reports to promote transparency and accountability in hiring. However, these efforts have had limited success in altering the structural forces that maintain racial inequities (Lapchick, 2023). Without enforcement mechanisms or incentives for genuine change, many institutions continue to favor traditional hiring practices.

Pipeline programs like the NCAA Champion Forum have attempted to prepare minority candidates for leadership roles, but the challenge remains deeply systemic and cultural.

The literature overwhelmingly indicates that the underrepresentation of Black head coaches in NCAA football is not a result of individual shortcomings but of institutionalized barriers embedded within the hiring culture, role assignments, and informal networks of college athletics. Institutional theory provides a robust lens through which these practices can be interrogated, while the concepts of racial tasking and social capital illuminate the specific mechanisms of exclusion. Future research must continue to center the lived experiences of minority coaches while advocating for structural interventions that move beyond surface-level diversity efforts toward systemic equity.

Methods

This qualitative study employed a phenomenological design to explore the lived experiences of African American assistant football coaches in NCAA Division I programs. Phenomenology was chosen to gain a deeper understanding of participants’ perceptions, interpretations, and feelings regarding their career trajectories and the systemic barriers they face in attaining head coaching positions (Moustakas, 1994; van Manen, 2016). The central research aim was to illuminate how race, role assignment, and institutional practices shape the professional realities of Black assistant coaches in predominantly White institutions (PWIs).

Phenomenological research allows for an in-depth examination of subjective experiences and is particularly effective in uncovering patterns and meanings behind social exclusion and inequity (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This approach was appropriate given the study’s focus on professional advancement within an

environment historically resistant to racial diversity in leadership (Cunningham, 2010). Institutional theory guided the framework, enabling interpretation of how norms and organizational structures sustain inequities in hiring and promotion (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983).

The study utilized purposive and snowball sampling to recruit ten African American male assistant coaches working within NCAA Division I football programs in the Southeastern United States. Purposive and snowball sampling are non-probability sampling methods in which participants are intentionally selected based on specific characteristics, and additional participants are recruited through referrals from initial subjects (Coombs et al., 2023). Participants were required to (a) self-identify as African American or Black, (b) have held a coaching position at the NCAA Division I level within one of the southern athletic conferences, (c) possess a minimum of five years of coaching experience, and (d) have applied at least once for a head coaching position. Recruitment efforts included direct email outreach to athletic departments, personal referrals, and informational flyers.

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews conducted via Zoom, each lasting approximately 60 to 90 minutes. Interview questions addressed themes such as professional aspirations, experiences with hiring committees, perceptions of racial bias, and access to mentorship and networking opportunities. An open-ended follow-up questionnaire was also distributed via email to allow participants to expand on their thoughts after the interview. All interviews were audio-recorded with consent and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

A descriptive phenomenological approach guided data analysis (Moustakas, 1994). Using NVivo software, transcripts were coded in multiple phases. Open coding was used initially to identify significant statements, followed by axial coding to

group related concepts into broader themes. Bracketing was employed to minimize researcher bias by consciously setting aside prior assumptions about the phenomenon (van Manen, 2016). Triangulation across interview and questionnaire data enhanced the study's trustworthiness and credibility (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

This study received Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval prior to data collection. All participants were provided informed consent documents outlining the purpose of the study, voluntary participation, and confidentiality measures. Pseudonyms were used in reporting to protect participant identity.

Results

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of African American assistant coaches in NCAA Division I football programs, with specific focus on their perceptions of leadership opportunities, encounters with racial tasking, and strategies for professional advancement. Data were collected from ten African American male assistant coaches and analyzed using a phenomenological approach. NVivo software facilitated thematic coding of interview transcripts and follow-up questionnaires, yielding four central themes: (1) Limited Opportunities for Leadership, (2) Stereotypical Role Assignments and Racial Tasking, (3) Navigating Institutional Politics, and (4) Emotional Labor and Resilience.

Theme 1: Limited Opportunities for Leadership

Participants consistently described an institutional environment where access to leadership roles was systematically constrained. Although all participants held significant coaching experience—many with more than a decade of service—the majority had never been seriously considered for head coaching roles. One participant summarized the situation by stating, “They

tell you to be patient and keep your head down. But the opportunities keep passing you by, especially when the big jobs open up.”

Multiple coaches noted the prevalence of hiring practices that favor internal networks or recycled candidates. As one coach explained, “ADs go with who they know. It’s a buddy system, and we’re not part of that circle.” Coaches emphasized that, even when their resumes matched or exceeded those of selected candidates, they were often overlooked unless a diversity initiative required interviews with minority candidates. Participants referenced the “token interview” phenomenon, whereby institutions comply with diversity policies in form but not in substance.

Additionally, participants noted that job postings for head coaching positions often appeared after candidates had already been informally chosen. These “performative searches,” as one participant called them, created a sense of futility and contributed to skepticism about institutional commitments to equity.

Theme 2: Stereotypical Role Assignments and Racial Tasking

Racial tasking emerged as a critical theme across all ten interviews. Participants described being routinely placed in roles associated with discipline, motivation, or recruiting—positions that aligned with racial stereotypes rather than their actual expertise. As one coach expressed, “They put you in charge of ‘keeping the kids in line’ or sending you into Black neighborhoods to recruit. But play-calling? That’s reserved for someone else.”

Several coaches felt boxed into roles that, while valuable, did not prepare them for head coaching trajectories. The lack of access to coordinator positions, which are widely viewed as stepping stones to head coaching roles, was a recurrent concern.

“If you’re not a coordinator, you’re not in the pipeline. It’s that simple,” said one participant.

One particularly revealing account came from a coach who had served over a decade at multiple institutions but had never been given play-calling responsibilities. “I’ve trained coordinators. I’ve built entire defensive systems. But they bring in someone else when it’s time to hand over the reins—someone that looks like the head coach,” he said.

This type of racialized role placement contributes to what participants termed a “glass sideline”—an invisible barrier that prevents Black coaches from transitioning to leadership roles despite their experience and capability.

Theme 3: Navigating Institutional Politics

Participants emphasized that success within the coaching profession required not only skill but also political navigation of institutional cultures. Athletic departments were often described as environments steeped in unspoken rules and informal hierarchies. One participant likened it to “walking a tightrope—one wrong move, one misunderstood comment, and you’re off the radar.”

Coaches described a need to constantly manage impressions, especially in predominantly White institutions where cultural misunderstandings could be magnified. Several reported adjusting their language, tone, and mannerisms in staff meetings and public engagements to appear “non-threatening” or “professional.” These adaptations were not merely tactical but emotionally draining.

A common narrative across interviews was that speaking out about inequity often resulted in being labeled “difficult” or “ungrateful.” One coach shared, “You want to speak up when you see patterns of

unfairness, but you learn quickly that being vocal can get you pushed out—or passed over.”

Additionally, participants discussed how institutional politics affected mentorship. While mentorship was viewed as essential for advancement, most coaches lacked access to high-level mentors who could advocate for them in decision-making spaces. “There’s no one in the room fighting for you,” said one participant. “You’re just hoping someone takes a chance.”

Theme 4: Emotional Labor and Resilience

The emotional toll of navigating racialized workspaces emerged as a final theme. Coaches reported feelings of frustration, self-doubt, and fatigue stemming from their repeated exclusion from leadership conversations. “Every time you think you’ve done enough to get the next opportunity, the goalposts move,” one coach lamented. Another added, “It wears you down. You question your value, your purpose.”

Yet, despite these challenges, participants also demonstrated significant resilience and commitment. Many spoke about staying in the profession to serve as role models for younger Black athletes. “Even if I never get a head job, I want these kids to see what’s possible,” said one coach. Others described a sense of calling, feeling that their presence alone challenged the status quo and carved a path for future generations.

Spirituality, family support, and peer solidarity were frequently cited as coping mechanisms. A number of coaches also mentioned creating informal support networks with other minority staff members to share advice and encouragement. These networks, though informal, offered a crucial source of validation in an otherwise isolating professional environment.

Cross-Theme Insights

Taken together, the four themes present a complex portrait of African American assistant coaches who are highly qualified yet structurally sidelined. Their experiences reflect a coaching landscape shaped by institutional inertia, racial coding of labor, and implicit bias. The insights provided by participants go beyond individual grievances and instead reveal broader systemic issues that demand structural intervention.

While each theme stands independently, they are interwoven. For example, the racial tasking that limits coaching development also reinforces the institutional patterns that prevent access to leadership. Similarly, the absence of meaningful mentorship exacerbates the emotional strain of navigating a biased system.

One participant summarized the convergence of these barriers succinctly: “They tell you to stay ready, but they never call your number. And eventually, you wonder if the game is rigged.”

The findings of this study reveal that leadership access for Black coaches in NCAA football is structurally constrained by informal hiring practices, recycled candidate pools, and performative diversity efforts that lack genuine commitment to equity. Racial tasking further impedes career advancement by relegating Black coaches to stereotypical roles that do not serve as stepping stones to head coaching positions. Navigating institutional politics requires significant emotional labor, as coaches must constantly manage perceptions and conform to unspoken norms—often at the expense of their authenticity and well-being. Yet, in the face of these persistent barriers, participants consistently demonstrated resilience, drawing strength from personal conviction, peer support networks, and a deep sense of responsibility to pave the way for future generations. Collectively, these findings underscore the entrenched nature of racial

inequity in collegiate football leadership and point to the urgent need for structural reforms that go beyond symbolic gestures.

Discussion

This study explored the lived experiences of African American assistant coaches in NCAA Division I football through a qualitative phenomenological approach. Participants shared stories of professional frustration, exclusion, and resilience while navigating systemic barriers within predominantly White athletic departments. The four emergent themes—limited opportunities for leadership, stereotypical role assignments (racial tasking), institutional politics, and emotional labor—paint a consistent picture of a racially stratified leadership structure in college football. These findings not only affirm existing research on underrepresentation in sport leadership (Cunningham, 2010; Lapchick, 2023) but also expand understanding by centering the emotional, political, and strategic efforts Black coaches must exert to simply remain in contention for promotion.

Interpreting the Themes Through Institutional Theory

Institutional theory provides a robust framework for interpreting how these barriers persist. This theory suggests that organizations maintain legitimacy by replicating familiar cultural norms and expectations (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). In NCAA football, this means that athletic departments often hire coaches who “look like” previous successful leaders—overwhelmingly White males. The majority of participants in this study reported that hiring decisions often favored White candidates with less experience but stronger proximity to existing power networks. This reflects the process of institutional isomorphism, where organizational practices are guided less by meritocratic principles and more by tradition and informal codes of behavior.

The token interviews described by participants—where Black candidates were invited to fulfill diversity requirements but not seriously considered—also align with institutional theory’s depiction of symbolic compliance. Organizations may adopt superficial diversity policies to appear progressive without truly disrupting embedded power hierarchies (Singer & Cunningham, 2012). The performance of inclusion becomes a tool for maintaining exclusion.

Moreover, the lack of racial diversity on search committees and the closed-loop nature of hiring in football—a sport deeply reliant on “coaching trees” and network referrals—intensifies these patterns. Even well-qualified Black coaches find themselves locked out of these networks, reinforcing the very structures that institutional theory predicts will resist meaningful change.

Racial Tasking and Role Stratification

One of the study’s most powerful findings was the consistent experience of racial tasking. Participants described being relegated to roles that reinforced racial stereotypes: disciplinarians, recruiters, or player liaisons. While these roles are critical to team function, they do not provide the leadership development or strategic oversight necessary to transition into head coaching positions.

These findings confirm previous research that documents the disproportionate placement of Black coaches in non-decision-making roles (Borland & Bruening, 2010; Singer, 2005). The continued exclusion from coordinator positions—a typical precursor to head coaching—reflects broader societal narratives that associate intellectual and leadership capacities with whiteness (Bonilla-Silva, 2014). As one participant in this study noted, “You can run the room, but you’ll never get the keys.”

Racial tasking not only affects professional development but also reinforces stereotypes for the next generation of athletes and coaches. When Black players consistently see White men in decision-making roles and Black men in supporting positions, it subtly communicates a racial hierarchy within leadership. Breaking this cycle requires institutional acknowledgment of how racialized labor roles are constructed and sustained within athletic programs.

The Weight of Politics and Emotional Labor

Participants' descriptions of institutional politics reveal the extent to which Black coaches must engage in image management and strategic self-censorship. The need to navigate perceptions of being "angry," "aggressive," or "too vocal" aligns with research on role congruity and the penalties associated with violating racialized expectations (Eagly & Karau, 2002). Black coaches walk a tightrope—speaking out risks retribution, but silence reinforces marginalization.

This tension produces a form of emotional labor, where coaches must regulate their expressions, moderate their tone, and downplay their frustrations to remain professionally viable. Hochschild (1983) originally described emotional labor in service work, but it is equally applicable in coaching, where image and perception can determine one's future. For Black coaches, this labor is intensified by the added pressure of racial representation. Many feel a responsibility not only to their own careers but to those who follow.

The absence of formal mentorship programs for minority coaches exacerbates this issue. Mentorship is critical for advancement in coaching, yet most participants lacked advocates in leadership positions. Their exclusion from these informal relationships further underscores the ways in which institutional culture privileges familiarity over fairness.

Resilience and Resistance

Despite these systemic barriers, participants exhibited remarkable resilience. They remained committed to their roles, often motivated by a desire to serve as role models for the players they coached. This form of resistance—continuing to excel despite structural exclusion—should not be romanticized, but it does highlight the emotional and moral clarity many Black coaches bring to their work.

The formation of informal peer support networks emerged as a valuable coping strategy. These communities provided validation, professional guidance, and emotional solidarity. In the absence of institutional support, these grassroots efforts are critical. However, reliance on informal networks should not be seen as a substitute for systemic reform. Black coaches should not have to self-organize survival strategies to withstand the inequities embedded in their institutions.

Conclusion

This study makes a significant contribution to the expanding body of literature on diversity in sport leadership by centering the voices of African American assistant coaches—individuals who have long been underrepresented in both scholarship and leadership roles within NCAA Division I football. While previous research has provided important statistical insights into racial disparities (Lapchick, 2023; Robinson & Hale, 2020), it has often lacked the qualitative depth needed to understand how these inequities are experienced on a personal and professional level. By adopting a phenomenological approach, this study bridges that gap, offering a narrative-rich exploration of how systemic exclusion, racial coding, and institutional inertia shape the careers and aspirations of Black coaches.

More than just documenting disparities, this research affirms the importance

of epistemological diversity in sport management scholarship, as emphasized by Singer (2005). It illustrates that systemic inequities cannot be fully grasped through data alone—they must be interrogated through the lived experiences of those directly affected. The stories shared by participants offer invaluable insight into the emotional, political, and strategic labor required to remain visible, viable, and hopeful in a system not built for their success.

By linking Institutional Theory with Critical Race frameworks such as racial tasking and interest convergence (Bell, 1980), this study provides a multidimensional perspective on how power operates in collegiate athletics. Institutional norms often masquerade as tradition, while informal hiring practices and implicit biases are masked by superficial commitments to diversity. These findings are particularly relevant for university administrators, athletic directors, and hiring committees seeking to move beyond performative inclusion and toward authentic, measurable change.

To that end, several practical recommendations emerge from this study. Hiring committees must be restructured to include racially diverse members with real coaching and leadership experience to ensure that representation is substantive, not symbolic. Formal mentorship and sponsorship programs are needed to connect Black assistant coaches with senior advocates who can offer strategic career guidance and advancement opportunities. Institutions must adopt transparent and equitable hiring processes that resist the tendency toward pre-determined outcomes. Additionally, leadership development pipelines must be intentionally designed to prepare assistant coaches from underrepresented backgrounds for coordinator and head coaching roles. Implicit bias and racial coding training should be mandatory for all administrators involved in hiring decisions.

Finally, diversity metrics must be tied to institutional accountability and publicly reported to ensure ongoing progress. These recommendations, if implemented, have the potential to transform not just the careers of individual coaches, but the broader culture of leadership in NCAA athletics.

Ultimately, this study underscores the persistent underrepresentation of Black head coaches and the structural forces that perpetuate this imbalance. Through the voices of assistant coaches, we come to understand how exclusion is normalized, how potential is overlooked, and how resilience becomes a necessary tool for survival. Institutional theory helps expose how these inequalities are perpetuated under the guise of tradition and cultural fit, while racial tasking reveals the mechanisms that keep Black coaches on the margins of leadership. Without deliberate structural intervention, these patterns will remain entrenched, continuing to disadvantage qualified professionals on the basis of race.

And yet, amidst these challenges, a powerful narrative of strength emerges. The participants in this study remain deeply committed to their profession, their athletes, and the vision of a more equitable future. Their perseverance should not be interpreted as complacency but as a profound form of resistance. It is now incumbent upon the NCAA and its member institutions to match that resilience with action—to rewrite the playbook of leadership and ensure that excellence, not race, determines opportunity.

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